

SNP analysis of *TLR4* promoter and its transcriptional factor binding profile in relevance to bovine subclinical mastitis

Rahil Razak Bhat^{a*}, Nadiem Nazir Bhat^a, Ambreen Shabir^b, Manzoor ur Rahman Mir^a, Sheikh Bilal Ahmad^a, Ishraq Hussain^a, Shahzada Mudasar^a, Syed Ashaq Hussain^c, Pervaiz Ahmad Dar^d, and Nuzhat Showkat^a.

^a Division of Veterinary Biochemistry F.V.Sc & AH, SKUAST-Kashmir, 190006, India

^b Division of Fish genetics and Biotechnology, FoFY, SKUAST-Kashmir, 190006, India

^c Division of clinical medicine, ethics and jurisprudence, F.V.Sc & AH, SKUAST-Kashmir, 190006, India

^d KVK-Ganderbal SMS, SKUAST-Kashmir, 190006, India

*Corresponding author: Rahil Razak Bhat. Email: rahilrazak192@gmail.com

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL 1

Genomic sequence with 2000bp promoter region with promoter upstream -2000bp.

Promoter (2000bp) and genomic sequence of *TLR 4* *Bos taurus*.

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>NC_037335.1:107055826-107068842 Bos taurus isolate L1
Dominette 01449 registration number 42190680 breed
Hereford chromosome 8, ARS-UCD1.2, whole genome shotgun sequence
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(<https://genome.ucsc.edu/>)

5` UTR

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Protein sequence of bovine TLR4 : 841 amino acids

>ABH09760.1 toll-like receptor 4 [Bos taurus]

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CDS TLR4 Gene (nucleotide sequence)

**>DQ839567.1:471-563,5112-5278,8028-10293 Bos taurus
toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4) gene, complete cds**

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Supplementary figures : S (1-3):

Figure S1: Representative figure of multiple alignment of PPR1 sequences in Bio-edit
**white high lightened area encompasses SNP at a position*

Figure S2: Representative figure of multiple alignment of PPR2 sequences in Bio-edit

Figure S2 continue below

Figure S3: Representative figure of multiple alignment of 5' UTR

Figure S3 continue below

Mode: Select / Slide Selection: 0 Sequence Mask: None Start ruler at: 1
Position: Numbering Mask: None

g d p GAT TAA
GCT CAA

Scroll speed: slow fast

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177	G	GG	GG	G	A	AG	GG	G	AGA	G	AA	GG	GG	A	GAGGGA	AAA	A	A	GAGAAA	GAAAG	A	GAAA	AAGG	G	AA	AA
178	G	GG	GG	G	A	AG	GG	G	AGA	G	AA	GG	GG	A	GAGGGA	AAA	A	A	GAGAAA	GAAAG	A	GAAA	AAGG	G	AA	AA
179	G	GG	GG	G	A	AG	GG	G	AGA	G	AA	GG	GG	A	GAGGGA	AAA	A	A	GAGAAA	GAAAG	A	GAAA	AAGG	G	AA	AA
180	G	GG	GG	G	A	AG	GG	G	AGA	G	AA	GG	GG	A	GAGGGA	AAA	A	A	GAGAAA	GAAAG	A	GAAA	AAGG	G	AA	AA
182	G	GG	GG	G	A	AG	GG	G	AGA	G	AA	GG	GG	A	GAGGGA	AAA	A	A	GAGAAA	GAAAG	A	GAAA	AAGG	G	AA	AA
183	G	GG	GG	G	A	AG	GG	G	AGA	G	AA	GG	GG	A	GAGGGA	AAA	A	A	GAGAAA	GAAAG	A	GAAA	AAGG	G	AA	AA
184	G	GG	GG	G	A	AG	GG	G	AGA	G	AA	GG	GG	A	GAGGGA	AAA	A	A	GAGAAA	GAAAG	A	GAAA	AAGG	G	AA	AA
185	G	GG	GG	G	A	AG	GG	G	AGA	G	AA	GG	GG	A	GAGGGA	AAA	A	A	GAGAAA	GAAAG	A	GAAA	AAGG	G	AA	AA
187	G	GG	GG	G	A	AG	GG	G	AGA	G	AA	GG	GG	A	GAGGGA	AAA	A	A	GAGAAA	GAAAG	A	GAAA	AAGG	G	AA	AA